

The Difference Between Classical and Quantum Dynamic Probability

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In classical mechanics, one follows a particle through $x(t)$. If one wishes to create a spatial probability for a constant p, v , this is $P(x)dx = dx/L$, where L is length, but this is a classical dynamic probability because it uses dt in fixed dx 's as probability. This means that the particle is moving with constant p, v , but one does not know the value of p or v . Furthermore, $dx \rightarrow 0$ so there is really no sense of ruler gradations. We argue, however, that the main issue with $P(x) = 1/L$ is that it does not lead to probability calculations. It is a consequence of $x = vt$ and not an independent idea which could be used to generate probability in certain dynamical problems.

In quantum mechanics, ruler gradations are important and are described by $\exp(ipx)$ which has gradation separations of \hbar/p with px having equal weight/entropy between gradations. Physically, it seems that these gradation separations are very important, not just for n -slit interference, but for dynamical problems which involve motion in space. It is not v which is key in these problems, but rather p (momentum). As a result, one might think that one only needs to use the dynamic quantum probability $\exp(ipx)$ or $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$. If, however, one has a localized problem, the classical dynamical idea of the amount of time a particle spends in different dx regions seems to make sense physically. For a free particle, one may obtain this value using $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$, but if one has a mixed situation $a(p_1)\exp(ip_1x) + a(p_2)\exp(ip_2x)$, the different gradations do not allow for all x points to have the same value because there is a net momentum $|p_1 - p_2|$ for some terms of W^*W . In other words, if one uses a stroboscope to freeze out rotation for one frequency, this frequency does not work for if there is a second frequency in the problem.

These lead to physical crests in space even though one is trying to consider relative probabilities which do not depend on gradation markings. It seems that if one has mixed gradation markings then even trying to remove them leads to $|p_1 - p_2|$ terms which represents a net momentum corresponding to a gradation separation which cannot be removed. In other words, the gradation spacing of the quantum $\exp(ipx)$ is important not only for dynamical problems (which we discuss), but even for relative time spent in x regions.

Classical Dynamical Probability

The classical probability distribution (1):

$$P(x)dx = dx/L \text{ for constant } p, v \text{ or } P(x)dx = Cdx/|v(x)| \quad ((1))$$

seems to have a fundamental problem, it is not used to calculate probabilistic events which occur in dynamics. Furthermore, it is not linked at all with any kind of spatial resolution, which in principle occurs through measurement and may occur through self-measurement if one has a particle in motion with constant p, v . It is simply a consequence of the deterministic $x = vt$ and does not represent any new independent information.

We have argued in previous notes that a particle creating its own spatial gradations while still having equal probability to be at any x between gradations is described by the math function $\exp(i b x)$. If one notes that $\exp(ib_1x)\exp(ib_2x)=\exp(i (b_1+b_2)x)$, then one has a conserved quantity b and p (momentum) is the only dynamical variable that is always conserved. As a result, there is probability in space in order to create gradations of width \hbar/p , but this probability also applies to physical problems. For example, it applies to an n -slit experiment and one dimensional reflection-refraction, whereas $P(x)=1/L$ does not. Thus, using a probability linked to a gradation leads to other probabilities through continuity of $\exp(ipx)$ and its first derivative or through interference of different $\exp(i p \cdot r_1) + \exp(p_2 \cdot r_2)$ etc.

Furthermore, as we have argued before, $P(x)dx=dx/L$ is really a distribution which applies to static objects. There is no dynamic sense to it, we argue.

We argue that even though x points have the same weight in between gradations, that frequency p is important as will be seen in the next section.

Quantum $\exp(ipx)$ and Freezing Out Gradations

Given $\exp(ipx)$, gradations of size \hbar/p are created with the angle px representing equal probability and a cycle, a new gradation. In other words, it is momentum, p , which is creating the gradations and if one wishes to freeze them out and only see the equal x weights, one may use:

$$\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = 1 \quad ((2))$$

An interesting feature, however, arises if one has mixed gradations, i.e.

$$a(p_1) \exp(ip_1x) + a(p_2) \exp(ip_2x) \quad ((3))$$

First, one may note that ((3)) may physically arise if there is a source of impulses in the scenario. The point seems to be that the x points have equal weights within gradations, but there are two gradations \hbar/p_1 and \hbar/p_2 . These are linked to two different frequencies (so to speak), p_1 and p_2 . Trying to freeze out p_1 (like with a stroboscope) means using a frequency of p_1 , but this does not freeze out p_2 motion and vice versa. Thus, an attempt to freeze out gradations in ((3)) leads to:

$$a(p_1)^*a(p_1) + a^*(p_2)a(p_2) + a(p_1)a(p_2) 2\cos((p_1-p_2)x) \quad ((4))$$

In other words, the mixed gradations actually lead to spatial probability even when one tries to freeze out such gradations.

((3)) may be extended to the more general bound state wavefunction: $W(x)= \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$.

Probabilistic Situations in the Physical World

Classical mechanics does not seem to carry a built-in probabilistic nature. Even $P(x)=1/L$ is simply a comparison of relative times governed by the forces in the problem. This probability itself does not seem to impose any independent conditions on situations in the physical world.

The gradation generating probability, however, does. In the case of a 2-slit experiment, if the slits are about \hbar/p apart, a distance linked to $\exp(ipx)$, then one may add $\exp(ip \cdot r)$ for each slit. In other words, the uncertainty in space due to creating gradations means that one may react (cannot distinguish) between the two slits. Thus, it is the \hbar/p linked with $\exp(ipx)$ which leads to the probabilistic nature of an interaction with two slits, \hbar/p apart. Classical mechanics would simply follow a particle through one slit or another.

Another example involves continuity of $\exp(ipx)$'s and their first derivatives as in a one-dimensional reflection-refraction problem. $P(x)=1/L$ leads to no useful result, whereas the gradation creating probability describes the dynamical situation:

$$A\exp(ipx) + B\exp(-ipx) = C\exp(ip2x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((5)) \text{ and its first derivative evaluated at } x=0$$

Another case for which the dynamical $\exp(ipx)$ solves a physical problem is that of a bound problem. In such a case, one uses:

$$W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((6))$$

One does not take $W^*(x)W(x)$ at the outset, but tries to solve for $a(p)$ in a dynamical manner by allowing the various $\exp(ipx)$ s (rotating rays) to interfere, but to use $\exp(ipx)$ as the probability associated with $pp/2m$, i.e.

$$KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E_n \text{ and } KE_{ave}(x) = \left\{ \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)pp/2m \right\} / \left\{ \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx) \right\} \quad ((7))$$

In other words, it is the different gradations which lead to interference even for constant p values. P_x represents equal x points, but only between gradations and so different gradations actually treat space in a different manner.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the classical dynamical probability $P(x)=1/L$, where L is length, has a problem because it does not lead to probability calculations. We suggest that space must be associated with a ruler gradation and that a moving particle creates a gradation through the math function $\exp(ipx)$, with p (momentum) representing a conserved quantity. This function leads to a gradation of \hbar/p which suggests that interactions with different objects within that region could lead to probabilistic results as in the n -slit situation.

We argue that $\exp(ipx)$ represents gradations with equal probability for x between different gradations. A 2π revolution represents adding a new gradation. Physically, $\exp(ipx)$ is like a rotating ray with frequency $\exp(ipx)$. $\exp(ip1x)$, however, is like another ray with a different

frequency. One may freeze out the rotation using $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$, but one needs a different frequency for $\exp(ip1x)$. In other words, if one has $\exp(ipx) + \exp(ip2x)$, one cannot use one frequency to freeze out rotation, i.e. remove gradations. This leads to a frozen out probability of: $(\exp(ipx)+\exp(ip1x)) * (\exp(ipx)+\exp(ip1x))$. This probability shows spatial changes even though $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(ip1x)$ treated separately do not. As a result, the dynamical creation of gradations through $\exp(ipx)$ is very important. It leads to probability crests and troughs in bound problems.

Finally, continuity of $\exp(ipx)$ s and their first derivatives leads to probability values for a one dimensional reflection-refraction problem.

In other, words, we argue that a probability expression should lead to probability calculation which is what occurs with $\exp(ipx)$, but not with $P(x)=1/L$. $\exp(ipx)$ is a driver of probability because it creates gradations in space which represent ruler markings and so represents an independent feature which leads to probabilistic results in certain physical interactions.

References

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